

A curious step-well stone inscription of V. S. 1535

PUSHPA PRASAD

Aligarh

A stone inscription was found in the niche to the left of steps in a step-well at the village of Singhpur in Mungoali tehsil, Guna district (Madhya Pradesh). It was first reported in the *Annual (Archaeological) Report from Gwalior State in 1924-25*.¹ I obtained a photograph of the inscription owing to the courtesy of Chief Epigraphist's Office, Mysore.

Thirty-six lines are written in Sanskrit with much mixture of local dialect. The first sixteen lines contain Sanskrit verses and the remaining portion is in prose largely in the local dialect. The characters are Nagari. The letters are not well formed, and the record is on the whole carelessly written. A portion of the record could not be deciphered. It is dated Samvat year 1535, the fifth day of bright half of the month Magh, Thursday; the date accords with 28th January 1479 A. D.²

The inscription informs us that the step-well was constructed by Rajmati *Bhatini*¹ daughter of Bhairavadas, son of Uvara, son of Chajjala of Sirohanagar (Siroha). It claims that several Muslim rulers of different region sent gifts to Rajmati for the construction of the garden, temple and step-well. These are named as Sher Khan of Chanderi, Ghiyasuddin of Mandoa (Mandu) Hussain Sahi of Jaunpur² Barbak³ of Pandua⁴ (Pandu), Tuhgluq Sahi of Thatta,⁵ and Qutubuddin of Gujarat.¹ Among the donors are also included an unnamed king of Bidar, (also designated Sultan of Bahmani) and a Sultan of Delhi. The named rulers are not exactly contemporaneous, though it is possible that the alleged gifts came over a long period, say 1440-70.

The inscription makes the interesting claim that Rajmati's father Bhairavadas was the *daraugi (darogha)* of Sultan Mubarak Shah² (Sultan Mamarakh Sahi) of Delhi.

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Rajmati Bhatni must have enjoyed the favour of the Sultan of Malwa since her son Ram Chandra described as a poet of repute (*mahakavi*), is said to have obtained the favour of Sultan Ghiyasuddin and (Prince) Nasiruddin. Ghiyasuddin, of the Khalji dynasty, was the ruler of Malwa from 1469 to 1500.¹⁰ Nasiruddin who was Ghiyasuddin's second son is referred to in the inscription without title of Sultan. Indeed he ascended the throne in 1500 much after the date of this inscription. Reference to him in this inscription accords with the known fact that Nasiruddin had acquired a dominant position in the Malwa kingdom immediately after his father's accession.¹¹

The gifts of the rulers are said to comprise palanquins, horses, elephants besides gems, pearls, gold *tankas* etc. (lines No. 20 to 25). Obviously, a very elevated status of almost 'national' calibre is being claimed for Rajmati Bhatni and her family members.

The village 'Sirohanagar' mentioned in the inscription as the place of origin of the family was an important place during 10th and 12th centuries. There are scattered and ruined remains of images, sculptors and a well.¹² It lies within Shivapuri town, three miles north west of Narwar at the bank of Sindh river.¹³

The place Singhpur where the step-well, garden and temple were constructed was also an important place since numerous historical monuments of 15th-16th centuries are found here.¹⁴ It is about six km. to the south-west of the celebrated fort of Chanderi.¹⁵

It seems that Rajmati had migrated from Siroha to Singhpur, ruled over by Sher Khan the *muqta* of Chanderi under Sultan Ghiyasuddin of Malwa. Sher Khan is a historical figure of some importance in 15th century Malwa. In 1458-59 he was posted at Ahar with a strong army, and in 1461 he commanded the right wing of Sultan Mahmud Khalji's army in an expedition towards the Deccan.¹⁶ Thus, he had obtained considerable status before the date of this inscription. That he actually controlled Chanderi is established by an inscription of 1490 found at the Chanderi fort.¹⁷ Rajmati's father had left his property and gathered wealth in Gurjar¹⁸ country. Most likely that settling afterward Singhpur, the family obtained the protection of Sher Khan, the commandant of Chanderi.¹⁹

The inscription (line 19) states that Sher Khan was kind to Rajmati and helped her in the construction of step-well. Sher Khan thus seems to have been a tolerant chief who is said to have caused the constructing of a royal temple, besides step-well (line 19).

The Sultan of Delhi whose name is not given in the inscription but is said to have made gifts to Rajmati, may possibly have been Bahadur Lodi, to judge from the date of the inscription (line 23).

The inscription makes a host of claims which it is difficult to credit. What one can say is that the family was originally of a rather low status to judge from the designation Bhatini given to Rajmati, but wedded to the muses. Quite possibly Rajmati was reputed singer patronised by Sher Khan; the fact that her husband is not mentioned, and her son was poet offer some clues as to her real position. Her father might have travelled to Gujarat and then to Delhi, seeking and obtaining royal or aristocratic patronage, and earning enough wealth to return to a town close to his place of birth. The wealth and possibly the county of Sher Khan, was responsible for the well, temple and garden. The claim that distant rulers sent gifts of the kind mentioned seems fantastic. And yet the fact that patronage of Muslim rulers should be proclaimed in such exaggerated manner is perhaps significantly indicative of the cultural environment of the time.

TEXT

१. ॥ औ ॥ सिद्धि गणेशाय नमः ॥ मल्लै शैलेन्द्र कल्पः शिश्रुरितर जनै पुष्प चापो (S) गंतामिर । योपैस्तु प्राकृतात्मा दिवि कुलिश भृता ॥
२. विश्वकायोपभेयः क्रुद्ध कंशेन (कंसेन) कालोभय चकित दृशा योगिमध्येयं मूर्तिः दृष्टारंगावतारे ह्ररिरमर गणानन्द कृत पातु युक्तया ॥१॥
३. स वो दिशतु भद्राणि । विघ्न वारणा वारणः । गणानां भुवनानां च नायकोपिविनायकः ॥२॥ शिरोह । (सिरोह) नगर वधूवदन चन्द्र बिम्बोद्गमैः
४. स्फुरत्तलतारकै ललितद्भुतं दृश्यते । दिवापि किलङ्गज्वलः सकल वन्दि वृन्दारकैः । सुरेन्द्रश्च पूजित समजनिष्ट तस्मिन् पु-
५. रे ॥३॥ यस्य श्रीङ्गजलस्य प्रति दिवसमभूत कीर्ति कर्पूर राशिर वक्त्रे दिक्कामिनी नां सुरमिति सुतरां दिग्गर्जर्वद्ध मानः । उद्ग्रीवा एवं कुंभरघल
६. बलद मल स्फार मुक्ता फलाद्यैः । क्रीडार्थं कोणिताक्षै गिरीशगिरि रिब प्रस्तुतो बक्ष्यमाणः ॥४॥ उवार इति नाम्नाभूत् तस्य पुत्रो महासयः । यस्य वा—
७. चं समाकर्ण्य च काक्षति बुधाः सुधाम् ॥५॥ तदात्मजौ भैरवनाम धेयः । श्री भैरवाराधन लब्ध सिद्धिः बभूव गो-धरणी धवानां सखा गुणानां निधिरेक एव ॥५॥
८. योनिः सृत्स्य गुप्त द्विद्यय विभवांता तस्य विद्या बलात् श्री मद्गूर्जर मेदिनी सनियतः । तद्भूपदत्तां श्रियां मारात्कुंजर केलि कौतिकवती हेम प्रभा

६. भास्वती । लब्ध्वा तीर्थ घरास्तुवा सम करोन् विप्रः समं पुण्य वाचां ॥७॥ भाग्येन तस्य सदनो (ने) तनया नयनां । यां ता सखी (शशि) मुखी कुल कैरवानां द्यौतिनी स्फुरति
१०. राजमतीनि नाम्ना व या धवल यत्य भुवाम रंगा ॥८॥ साशार देवशरदिंदु मुखी गुणानां । आवासभूमि रधि....गयासदीनां । वग्मिः सुधा कबलिवाभिरवा—
११. लक्ष्मी दुर्वार वारण घटा परिपालितां गां....॥९॥ यद्गोर्होर्धजनः प्रभात समये सर्वार्थमत्या दरात् । लब्ध्वा पूर्णमनोरथाः प्रतिदिनं गेहं ब्रजत्यात्मनः ।
१२. गंगे च मल जीवना नृपदिभिः संस्तूय माना सदा सैषा राजमती चिरं विजयतात्सर्वोपकार क्षमा ॥१०॥ तथा कारिता कापिका पुण्यतोया तृषां ताये विच्छेदिनी
१३. च ध्वगानां सुधा सार सौख्य प्रदाभाति भूमौ जगल्लोचना नन्द सन्दोह पूर्ण ॥११॥ नाना देशं समागताम् द्विजवरान् नाहूय वैदा क्षरैः
१४. पुन्येस्यात् सरसे तटेति (पुण्ये स्मिन् सरस स्तटेऽति) निकटै हैमी तुला कल्पिता । दत्ता चरुं ययार्थि भाग्य जननी विप्रेभ्य एव क्षणात् सैषा राजमती क्षितौ विजयतां सवाथ सिद्धि प्रदा ॥१२॥
१५. यत्तो यये प्रतिवासरे हिम रुचि र्गमन्तु इमा ननै रुन्मीलतरला यत मितिस्त तन्नेत्रां जनै निजितः ॥ व्याजेन प्रतिबिंबितो कमखिलं स्वं प्रोथितु प्रायशः ॥
१६. रात्रौ स्नाति पुनातिकं न विशद या वापिका सां प्रवं ॥१३॥ राजमती भाटिणी ताका ढिली दासु । सुलितान ममारख साहि के दर्रोगी । पिता भैरव
१७. दासु । तिहि की पुत्री राजमती । सुपुत्री गणण राशि चतुर विद्यापात्रा सुलक्षणा विद्यार्थणीदि सा....र को फिगणा हारि । अनेक गुण गरिष्ठा सु चंदेरी
१८. आइ रही । तिहि प्रस्वाई सरेषान मुक्ते तिहि राज मंदिरु घर करवाया । वागवाडी निवाण ताल बहुत कर वाये । सेर षान बहुत मया करता । जिसकुकी
१९.अर दासि करई राजमती केरे सुनिहाल होता सुसरेषा साह ने....सुचंदेरी चन्द्र । पुरी का
२०. साहिसु स्तु राजमती भाटिणी कदु बहुत करता । सु सुलितान गयासदीना । भाग्या । मोडागई अनेक रत्न मुक्ता फल सहिते....घर....दोप । पालिकी
२१. साहिता यह प्रसादु दीया । जिहि कीति आर्वरी करं हिति सुकदु निहाल करौ । जौणपुर का पातिसाहि भाग्या सुलितानु हिति सुलतान

२२. हस्ती मुक्ताफलामालिकीसहित दीया। तिहि बीछे पंचुवें का मतिसहि। मात्तक। साहि जाहू भाग्या। तिहि पातिसहि। अरव सहित पांच लक्ष।
२३. टंका हस्तीसहित दीया। तिहि बीछे सुलितानु कलोदिली का भाग्या २०० बुई सै घोड़े दीये। ठठ्टे का पातिसहि तुगलकु सहि। साबा लक्षु टंका दीया म गुजबस्ती।
२४. पाति सहि भाग्या। सुलितानु कतुबुदीना हदिनागेत। रडे। अलमधान। वा। साखिकी सहित। अनेक रत्न सहित जरीना व अरव दीए। विदर का पाति सहि बना।
२५. बहुमनी सुभाग्य म तिहि बहु प्रसादु करि एक लक्ष टंका की वस्तु दीई अनेक तीर्थ कीए। अनेक दन्त दीए। धर्मात्मा पुन्यत्मा "जहू की"।
२६. हू "सहोदर बड़े के। सवरु। तिहि अरु का जाऊ राज मंदिर भिता भैरौदासु। माता माणिक दो वहिनि भानमती भाई दासु ऐकु था। माणि जी इमयंती।
२७. आषणी राशि वैशाख। तिहि राजमती भाटिणी का सुपुत्र रामचन्द्र अनेक मुख गलिष्ट। महा कवि दाब मुन संयुक्त। परनारी सहोदर। माता।
२८. पिता भक्तु। अनेक कुटुम्ब सा। रहु। तिहि ककु सुलितान गयासद। सहि। निसारि। साहि। बहुत मया कीए। औसा सपूत हुवना। तिहि का वांष।
२९. वैणी दासु। तिहि का यह वागु वावडी राज मंदिर घर राजमती भाटिणी राशि कर न्वाया। तिहिक आगे राज पुत्रु वीवूडो डंकु रावगु था। सील—
३०. वंत अभयकारी "तिसु राजमती भाटिणी के आगे प्रधानु देवी दासु हुथा"। लाल पोरु स्वमिल उपगारी जनक हुजा
३१. "सो भणि। यह प्रधानु था। सडा रणि देवा खना। अलम लब्धा "कासीमरु बुरहा। मत सुषुमला या दास हुना था। सु फुर भाइसु करता।
३२.
३३.
३४. संवत १५३५ वर्षे माघ सुदि ५ शिशिर रितौ भाटिणी वाई राजमती वापिका कामिना शुभम्

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३५. सुलिवान साहि गयासदीमा
३६. गुणासुंदरो लिषिता ॥

TRANSLATIO :¹⁸

Om I Hail : Salute to Sri Ganesa.

- L. 1-2 Krishna in his incarnation as (Ranga natha) and who causes delight to the hosts of God and who is seen as a lofty mountain by the wrestlers, as a child by others, as Kamadeva by women, as cowherd by the common folk, as one who encampasses the entire Universe by the thunderbolt-bearing Indra, as the angry Death by Kamsa with eyes tremulous with fear, as one is worthy to be meditated upon by the Yogis, may protext us with application.¹
- L. 2-3 Vinayaka, who removes obstacles which are like elephant (or who is just like an elephant in the removal of obstacles); the leader of the Ganas and of the worlds, May show prosperity to all of you.²
- L. 4-5 Indeed, the city of Siroha looks marvellous in the day also, by the rise of the disc of the moon in the shape of women's faces, delightful with stars in the shape of clear and tremulous pupils of eyes. In that city Chajjala was born who, like Indra, is worshipped by the entire group of bards.³
- L. 5-6 Fame of that Chajjala is like a heap of camphor increasing every day in all directions, which are like fragrant faces of women. This heap of camphor, lofty like the Himalaya is seen with uplifted necks by the Diggajas, whose foreheads are covered with pure and radiant pearls.....and whose eyes are half closed sportively.⁴
- L. 6-7 A noble-minded son was born named Uvara. After listening to his speech learned men have no desire for nector.⁵
- L. 7- His son was named Bhairava. He achieved perfection through adoration of Sri Bhairava. He is the sole treasure of all virtues, the became the friend of earth, cows and kings.⁶
- L. 8-9 Who having left his house and wealth of his father, obtained through the power of his learning the Gurjara country, filled with eagerness towards the sport of nearby elephants, and the wealth, shining with the lustre of gold, given by that king (of

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Gurjara). This meritorious one made the place of pilgrimage equal (?) to Brahmins (filled the place of pilgrimage with Brahmins ?) ⁷

- L. 10 His daughter (born) through the good fortune of his policies...the moon faced one shining among her family member who are white lotuses, is known by the name of Rajamati, who, like moon light makes...white.⁸
- L. 11 She is like Sarasvati, and her face is as autumnal moon, welling place of good virtues ...Ghiyadjin...through her speech, made white (pure) by nectar obtained the earth, which was protected by the host (army) of irresistible elephants...⁹
- L. 11-12 In whose house each morning the supplicants having obtained all wealth along with respect, and (thus) having accomplished (their) desires, return to their houses. May she whose life is pure as Ganga, who is always praised by the kings, who is capable of doing all favours, be victorious for long time.¹⁰
- L. 13 This step-well, (*Vapika*) caused to be made by her, which removes with its water the traveller's thirst, which gives the pleasure of the essence of nectar, which is filled with the mass of delight of (all) the eyes of the world, is resplendent on this earth.¹¹
- L. 14 Having invited eminent Brahmins (here) from different countries through vedic syllables, she caused to be made, on the sacred bank of the pond close by, a golden weighing balance and gave immediately to the Brahmins this beautiful balance which produces wealth according to the supplicants.¹²
- L. 15-16 Every day the moon, defeated by the faces of women of Gaminlu (?) the faces which ...contained eye collyrium, takes a dip at night in the water of that step-well under the pretext of getting himself reflected in it, in order to wash himself thoroughly, Whom does that vast step-well not purify now.¹³ (*Sanskrit text ends here : dialect begins*)
- L. 17 Rajmati Bhatini observed that (her father Bhairav das was a *darraugi* of Sultan Mubarak Shah (Sultan Mamarakh Sahi), seated at Delhi (Dhilli).
- L. 18 His daughter's name was Rajmati, who was clever, beautiful, fortunate, a scholar and fostered with love and endearment.

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- L. 19 Several eminent persons came at Chanderi. From the eirs suggestions Sher Khan Mukta (*muqta*) made that royal temple and house as well as a garden and tank etc. Sher Khan had great sympathy for her. Rajmati requested him and (Sher Khan was) pleased (to do so).
- L. 20-21The fortunate Sultan Ghiyasuddin of Mandoai (Mandu) conferred this gift with several gems and pearls with a palanquin. Fierce...(people were) also pleased after describing...his fame. The august Sultan Hussain Sahi of Jaunpur.
- L. 22 gave several elephants, pearls, with a palanquin. Thereafter, the fortunate king Barbak Sahi of Pandua gave horses, elephant and five lakh *tankas* with palanquin.
- L. 23 Thereafter, the devoted and fortunate Sultan of Delhi gave two hundred horses. The august king Tughluq Sahi of (Tatta) Thatta gave one and a quarter lakh *tankas*.
- L. 24 The fortunate Sultan Outubuddin of Gujarat gave diamonds, gem and a whole mine with palanquin, severals pearls and gold with horses.
- L. 25 The king of Bidar, the fortunate Sultan of Bahamani, gave many gifts and things with one lakh *tankas*.....Pious and religious.....
- L. 26-27 The names of this family are as follows-father Bhairavadas, mother Manika, two sisters, Bhanmati (and Rajmati), one brother Dasu and niece Damyanti...collected their own money.
- L. 28 Rajmati Bhatini has a worthy son, named Ram Chandra, who possess good qualities, meritorious virtues, a brother for other women and devotee of mother and father, and a Mahakavi (great poet); and (who) got the favour from Sultan Ghiyasuddin Sahi and Nasiruddin Sahi.
- L. 29His brother was Benidas. Rajmati Bhatini constructed this garden, boali and royal temple with (that) money.
.....
- L. 30The Pradhan was Devidas.....Lal Khoru was the one soliciting the gift and.... Dashana.....
- L. 31The masons were Vurahmata, Sukhumala and Dashana.....

- L. 32
- L. 33-34In Samvat year 1535 on the fifth day of the bright half of Magh, in winter, Rajmati Bhatini has constructed this step-well (*Vapika*) May prosperous.
- L. 35Sulitana.....Sahi Ghiyasuddin
- L. 36Written by Guna Sundra.

REFERENCES :

1. *Annual Report of Gwalior State*, (GAR) 1924-25, No. 33, p. 34; See also D. R. Patil, *The Descriptive and Classified List of Ancient Monument in Madhya Bharat*, No. 1553, p. 128; and the *Annual Report of Indian Epigraphy*, 1966-67, No. B. 179.
2. In, GAR, 1924-25, No. 33, as well as Patil, the date of the inscription is wrongly given as Samvat 1525 (1468 A. D.); *op. cit.*, p. 128.
3. *Bhat* is a caste of bards and genealogists, who usually attached themselves to Rajputs R. V. Russell & Hiralal, *Tribes and Castes of Central Provinces of India*, II, p. 251-52; John Malcolm, *A Memoir of Central India Including Malwa*, (1832), II, p. 131-139. *Bhatini* was the word for a 'Bhat Woman; a female minstrel' in Gujarati, (*Modern Gujarati English Dictionary*, s. v.).
4. Hussain Shah was the Sultan of Jaunpur, 1458-1479. Firishta, *Tarikh-i Firishta*, translated by Briggs, *History of the Rise of the Mahommedan Power in India*, IV, p. 375.
5. Rukn-uddin Barbak Shah, son of Nasiruddin Mahmud, Sultan of Bengal ruled from 1459-1479. J. N. Sarkar, *History of Bengal*, p. 132-133.
6. Pandu is a deserted town in Malda district in Eastern Bengal and Assam. *The Imperial Gazetteer of India*, XIX, p. 392.
7. Tughluq Shah may be identified with Jam Tughluq Shah of Sindh of Samma dynasty who ruled from 1414-1442 A. D. Briggs, *op. cit.*, IV, p. 423.
8. Qutbuddin, Prince Jalal Khan, the eldest son of Muhammad Shah who assumed the title Qutubuddin Ahmad Shah II of Gujarat ruled from 1451-1459. Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 37.
9. Sultan Mubarak Shah may be identified with Sultan Mubarak Shah of Sayyid dynasty who ruled over Delhi 1421 to 1439 A. D.

A curious step-well stone inscription of V, S. 1535

10. Briggs, *op. cit.*, IV, p. 237; U. N. Day, *Medieval Malwa*, p. 220.
11. Day, *op. cit.*, p. 221-22; A. K. Majumdar, *The Sultanate of Delhi*, p. 181.
12. Patil, *op. cit.*, p. 128, No. 1561 to 1563; *GAR 1925-26*, p. 8.
13. *Survey of India Map*, No 54 c.
14. Patil, *op. cit.*, p. 128. No 389, 1558 to 1560, Cunningham *ASR*, II, p. 405.
15. *Survey of India map*, No. 54; Cunningham, *op. cit.*, pl. No. XCIII,
16. Day, *op. cit.*, p. 194, 151-52.
17. Cunningham mentions that a bilingual inscription of 1490 at a gateway of the Chanderi Fort records that Jiman Khan son of Sher Khan, governor of Chanderi, during the reign of Ghias Khan of Malwa, made this useful and costly work. *Op. cit.*, p. 406-07; *JASB*, II, p. 548; Day, *op. cit.* p. 234, 250-51.
18. Gurjar was the greater part of Khandesh and Malwa as well as Gujarat. N. L. Dey, *The Geographical Dictionary of Ancient and Medieval India*, p. 72-73, 236.
19. I am greatly indebted to Dr. S. R. Sharma, Department of Sanskrit, AMU, for guidance on several words and phrases.